

A New Parameter in Astatistical Stabilization of Ternary Complexes

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The formation constants of the complexes of the type $[CuAL]$, where A = 2,2'-bipyridyl (bipy), 1,10-phenanthroline (phen) and L = tryptophan have been determined in aqueous medium and $\mu = 0.2 M$ ($NaClO_4$) at 30° . The formation constant values have been determined by graphical method and further refined by using a computer program SCOGS. The value of $\Delta \log K$, $(\log K_{MAL}^M - \log K_{ML}^M)$, is found to be positive in $[CuAL]$ complexes even though L is coordinating through amino acid end just as glycine. The higher stabilization of the ternary complexes is mainly due to release of electron repulsion in the ternary complex. There is repulsion between $Cu(II)$ $d\pi$ electrons and electrons delocalized over the indole ring in binary complex. In the ternary complex, due to $M \rightarrow bipy$ π interaction, electrons pass over the bipyridyl molecule and there is less amount of electron repulsion leading to positive $\Delta \log K$.

VARIOUS aspects of the ternary complexes involving aromatic tertiary amines and various N-N, N-O⁻ and O-O⁻ coordinating ligands are being studied in detail because of the similarity of the aromatic tertiary amines with imidazole, which occurs commonly in biological systems. These complexes¹⁻³ provide models for metalloenzymes. Such complexes are also of interest as they exhibit an astatistical^{2,3} stabilization due to special role of the aromatic tertiary amines. In the complexes $[MAL]$, where A is a tertiary amine like 2,2'-bipyridyl (bipy), it has been observed that the mixed ligand formation constant $\log K_{MAL}^M$ is higher than that expected from statistical considerations⁴. This has been explained to be due to $M \rightarrow bipy$ π interaction^{5,6}. Consequently, effective electronegativity of $[MA]^{2+}$ is almost the same as in $[M(H_2O)_6]^{2+}$ and hence $\log K_{ML}^M \approx \log K_{MAL}^M$.

It has been further observed that $[MA]^{2+}$ complexes discriminate between secondary ligand (L) with coordinating sites, N-N, N-O⁻ and O-O⁻^{6,7-10}. In case where secondary ligand is malonate¹¹ coordinating through two oxygen atom, $\Delta \log K$, $(\log K_{MAL}^M - \log K_{ML}^M)$, is positive. Sigel has attributed the greater stabilization of ternary complexes containing O-O⁻ to an increase in class A character of $[M.bipy]$. In keeping with this concept we have extended an explanation in terms of electron repulsion¹²⁻¹⁴. In the formation of binary complexes, there is electron repulsion between the metal $d\pi$ electrons and the lone pair of electrons (if any) present on the σ bonding ligand L. However, in the ternary complexes, due to back donation of electrons through π bonding from the metal ion to the molecule A, the electron density on $[CuA]^{2+}$ is reduced. Therefore, the repulsion between the metal $d\pi$ electrons and the additional lone pair of electrons over the secondary ligand L is less in the ternary complexes. There is no extra lone pair of electrons present on σ bonding N atom and hence this effect is not felt in N-N coordinating ligands. In ligands

coordinating through N-O⁻ there is lone pair of electrons over the carboxylate O⁻. Due to the decrease of the electron repulsion in the ternary complexes, $\Delta \log K$ is much less negative in N-O⁻ than in N-N coordinating ligands. In case of O-O⁻ coordinating ligand like malonate, there are lone pairs of electrons over both carboxylate anions and hence the effect is more pronounced leading to positive $\Delta \log K$ in $[CuAL]$.

It has been further observed that in case where O-O⁻ is an aromatic ligand like $[Cu(bipy)(cat)]$, $\Delta \log K$ is more positive. This additional stabilization has been explained by Sigel¹⁵ in terms of interligand π interaction between two ligands through metal $d\pi$ orbitals. However, Sigel presumed that this interaction is not significant. Our studies of the electronic spectra of the complexes also do not indicate any significant inter-ligand π interaction. Hence an attempt has been made to explain the stabilization in the ternary complexes involving aromatic O-O⁻ also in terms of electron repulsion. Since the $Cu(II)$ electrons are in t_{2g} orbitals with π symmetry, the repulsion with the electrons on the p_z orbital of the coordinated O-O⁻ (catechol) will be more in the binary complex. Hence, there will be greater release of repulsion and stabilization of the ternary complexes wherein $d\pi$ electrons of $Cu(II)$ pass over the bipyridyl molecule. Another important observation made by Sigel¹⁶ and also by us¹⁷ is that electron withdrawing groups on L reduce the stability of ternary complexes while electron releasing groups on L increase the stability. This has also been explained¹⁷ in terms of the proposed electron repulsion concept. The electron withdrawing groups lower the electron density on the ligand atom. Hence, the electron repulsion in the binary complex is less and corresponding release of electron repulsion in ternary complex and its stabilization is less.

Normally, $\Delta \log K$ is found to be positive only

in cases where L is O-O⁻ coordinating ligands. It has been observed by us¹² that $\Delta \log K$ is positive in case of [CuAL] complex where A=2(2'-pyridyl)-benzimidazole and L=glycine having N-O⁻ coordinating site. This was explained to be due to increased Cu→A π interaction due to pyridyl and benzene rings of 2(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole. Further, it has been observed by us¹² that $\Delta \log K$ is positive in cases of [CuAL] complexes, where A=bipy or phen and L=phenylalanine, tyrosine or dopa, coordinating from N-O⁻ site as in the case of glycine. It has been shown that the aminocarboxylate end of phenylalanine, tyrosine or dopa coordinates with [CuA] and the phenyl, phenol or catechol part remains free and spreads over the [CuA] part. There may be an intermolecular stacking interaction between the tertiary amine and the aromatic ring of the secondary ligand as suggested by Sigel in case of [Cu(o-phen)(phenylacetate)] complexes¹⁹. However, construction of a model shows that the aromatic ring of the secondary ligand can spread only over the axial region of the Cu(II) and not beyond. The greater stability of these ternary complexes can be explained in terms of release of electron repulsion. There is repulsion in the binary complex between the Cu(II) electrons and π electrons of secondary ligand phenyl group which can come over the metal ion. But in the ternary complexes due to M→A π interaction, the electron density over Cu²⁺ ion is effectively reduced and hence repulsion is reduced leading to the formation of stable ternary complex. In order to confirm the observation further, in the present study mixed ligand complexes [CuA tryptophan], where A=bipy (A¹) or phen (A²), have been studied.

Experimental

All reagents used were of A.R. grade. The proton-ligand and metal-ligand formation constants were determined in aqueous medium and $\mu=0.2 M$ (NaClO₄) at 30°. The values of $\bar{n}H$, K_1^H , K_2^H , $\bar{n}$, p^L , $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were calculated by carrying out Irving-Rossotti titrations^{20,21}. The formation constants of ternary complexes were determined by using a modified Irving-Rossotti titration technique⁹.

All the formation constants were subjected to refinement by using the computer program SCOGS²². Details of consideration of various species and use of computer program is as described in our earlier work¹²⁻¹⁴. The refined constants are tabulated in Tables 1 and 2. It is observed that

TABLE 1—PROTONATION CONSTANTS AND METAL LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANT OF COPPER COMPLEXES IN AQUEOUS MEDIUM, I=0.2 MOL dm⁻³ (NaClO₄) AT 30°

Ligands	Protonation constant		Metal-ligand binary constant	
	K_1^H	K_2^H	K_1	K_2
A ¹	4.45 ± 0.01	1.5 ± 0.1	8.1 ± 0.01	5.5 ± 0.03
A ²	4.96 ± 0.01	1.9 ± 0.1	9.25 ± 0.02	4.54 ± 0.09
Tryptophan (L)	9.06 ± 0.03	2.6 ± 0.04	8.19 ± 0.09	6.79 ± 0.07

TABLE 2—STABILITY CONSTANT OF TERNARY COMPLEX AND LOG K IN AQUEOUS MEDIUM, I=0.2 MOL dm⁻³ (NaClO₄) at 30°

L ¹	CuA ¹ L ¹		CuA ² L ¹	
	$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$	$\Delta \log K$	$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$	$\Delta \log K$
L ¹	9.75 ± 0.03	+1.56	9.32 ± 0.03	+1.13

the major species are [CuA] and [CuAL] as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Variation of concentration of different species with pH.

Spectral measurement: The spectra were recorded on a Carl Zeiss Specord UV visible spectrophotometer with 1 cm quartz cells using water as solvent. Solutions of concentration 10⁻⁴ to 10⁻² mol dm⁻³ were used for uv and visible regions, respectively. Spectra of free ligands, mixture of two ligands, [CuA₂], [CuL₂] and [CuAL], prepared by direct mixing of Cu(II) and ligands in required proportions, were obtained. The observed band positions are tabulated in Table 3.

Results and Discussion

It is observed that tryptophan coordinates to the metal ion as bidentate ligand like glycine in binary complexes. The value obtained for $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ in the present study is 8.19 ± 0.09 (Table 1) and is very close to the reported value 8.27 ± 0.05²³. The position of the d-d band also confirms that the coordination sites in [Cu(tryptophan)₂] are N-O⁻. The observation of the d-d band in [Cu(tryptophan)₂] at 714 nm is very close to the d-d band in [Cu(gly)₂] (712.0 nm) and also confirms that the coordination sites are N-O⁻.

It is observed in the present study that $\Delta \log K$ is positive in the ternary complexes even though the coordination of tryptophan is from aminocarboxylate end. The higher stability of these ternary complexes can be explained by considering following factors. The aminocarboxylate part of tryptophan coordinates with [CuA] and the indole part remains free. This can spread over the bipyridyl base part and there may be intramolecular stacking interaction between these two parts which contributes to higher stability.

TABLE 3—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL BANDS (nm) OF FREE LIGANDS AND BINARY AND TERNARY Cu(II) COMPLEXES IN AQUEOUS MEDIUM

A ¹	233.6	284.1				
A ²	230.4	266.1				
Tryptophan (L ¹)	215.1	270.3	277.8	285.7 (sh)		
[CuA ₂] ¹	243.9	303.0	314.5	700		
[CuA ₂] ²	231.5	275.5	298.5 (sh)	699		
[CuL ₂] ¹	209.2	270.3	277.8	285.7	714.3	
A ¹ + L ¹	218.6	244.0 (sh)	285.7	305.3 (sh)	492.0 (sh)	
A ² + L ¹	222.2	268.5	290.0 (sh)	322.6	496.0 (sh)	
[CuA ¹ L ¹] ¹	217.4 (sh)	244.0 (sh)	258.0 (sh)	287.8	298.5, 310.3, 457.0 (sh), 682.6	
[CuA ² L ¹] ¹	212.8	270.3	289.9 (sh)	466.0 (sh)	685.0	

In mixed ligand complexes [Cu(ATP)(tryptophan)], it was observed by Sigel²³ that tryptophan coordinates through aminocarboxylate end. There is intramolecular stacking interaction between the indole moiety of tryptophan and purine moiety of ATP in these mixed ligand complexes i.e. these complexes can be considered as metal ion bridged stacking adducts. This contributes to the stability of ternary complexes. Due to this stacking interaction charge transfer band observed at 292 nm in a mixture of ATP⁴⁻+tryptophan is shifted to 295 nm (lower energy) in the ternary complex [Cu(ATP)(tryptophan)]. Similar type of stacking interaction is also observed in [Cu(ATP)(bipy)] complexes²⁴. In a mixture of ATP⁴⁻+bipy there is a new band at 295 nm, which is shifted to 313 nm (lower energy) in [Cu(ATP)(bipy)] ternary complex. This is due to stacking interaction between bipyridyl and the base part of ATP in the ternary complex.

In the present study, we observed a new band at 492 nm in a mixture of tryptophan and bipy. This is due to charge transfer interaction between base part of bipy and indole moiety of tryptophan. This new band is found to be shifted to 457 nm (higher energy) in mixed ligand complex [Cu(bipy)(tryptophan)]. This indicates that there is charge transfer interaction between the indole and bipy moiety in the ternary complex also. However, in the mixed complex the charge transfer band is shifted to higher energy region unlike in [Cu(ATP)(tryptophan)] and [Cu(ATP)(bipy)] complexes where charge transfer band moves to lower energy region. It can be explained by comparing with [Cu(bipy)(phenylalanine)] wherein it was considered that the phenyl part of alanine can not reach over bipyridyl. In tryptophan also (CH₂)₂ chain linking indole part with the nitrogen is as in phenylalanine. However, indole part has two rings. Hence, it may partly reach over bipyridyl and there may be a distant charge transfer interaction requiring higher amount of energy. This shows that the charge transfer interaction in the ternary complex [CuA-tryptophan] is reduced and hence may not contribute to the positive $\Delta \log K$ value.

The positive $\Delta \log K$ in this N-O⁻ coordinating ligand can be explained by considering that there is repulsion in the binary complex between the Cu(II) electrons and the indole ring electrons of tryptophan which can come over the metal ion as in case of Cu-phenylalanine, Cu-tyrosine, Cu-dopa. But in ternary complexes due to M → A_π interaction the electron density over Cu²⁺ ion is effectively

reduced and hence the repulsion is less in ternary complex. This lowering in electron repulsion stabilizes the complex formation and leads to positive $\Delta \log K$ in these ternary complexes even though the coordination is from N-O⁻ site²⁵.

These ternary complexes, involving two ligands of biochemical importance, thus exhibit interesting structural feature leading to stabilization of the ternary complexes.

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